

Reputation Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around reputation risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The research was conducted from 2002 to 2022, by searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Scopus, and WoS via the Perish/Harzing application, with the keyword "Reputation Risk". Based on the search results, there were 91 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to reputation risk is divided into 14 clusters and 78 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 5 main themes related to reputation risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Reputation Risk; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Literature Review; Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

Risk management in banking has improved in line with the development of the financial industry as a whole. In recent years, banks have begun to understand the importance of risk management to maintain business stability and continuity. This can be seen from the existence of regulations from the Financial Services Authority (OJK) which regulate risk exposure management and effective corporate governance. Risks in the financial sector must be recognized and controlled by estimating the potential that may occur in the future, not after the risk has already occurred. Therefore, a methodology for modeling risks that may occur in the future is very important so that those making decisions can prepare strategies to overcome future risks. One of the risks that occur in the financial industry is reputation risk. Reputation risk management involves identifying, assessing, controlling and monitoring these risks over time to ensure that the bank remains stable and maintains its reputation.

In previous research, there were several indicators of reputation risk in banking. First, transparency of financial information and collaboration with stakeholders. The need to pay attention to business ethics and good governance, including business sourcing and product marketing policies. Violations of business ethics can result in a low reputation for Islamic banking, even though it has a high reputation. Therefore, institutional owners must ensure to maintain their reputation by not violating business ethics. Second, the credibility of the owner and the company concerned, as well as events that affect reputation. One of the factors that causes an increase in reputation risk is the reputation of the owner of the institution. Credibility also plays an important role in influencing reputation, such as a bank that has many customers because of public trust in the institution. Third, materiality and frequency of reporting, type of media and coverage of reporting. Banking management during the assessment period can influence both positive and negative news coverage of the institution. Fourth, the number and level of customer use in choosing complex sharia bank products, as well as the amount and materiality of collaboration between sharia banks and their partners. Comprehensive product ownership and working with good business partners can pose reputational risks if there is a misunderstanding in the use of products or services by business partners.

Fifth, during the assessment period, the frequency of customer complaints is measured to determine the quality of service. The number of customer complaints does not always indicate that service is deteriorating, but further research is needed. However, if the number of bank customers increases, this could lead to a significant increase in the number of complaints.

Based on the problems above, it is necessary to map reputation risk management topics to identify, measure and control risks that will occur. This can fulfill the need for human resources tasked with risk management to have knowledge, skills and work attitudes according to the bank's needs. So, the aim of this research is to map research topics around reputation risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking by using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature review study to analyze, identify and review articles from indexed international journals and accredited national journals.

Literature Review

Reputational risks are risks that arise to a bank's reputation due to unethical business practices, internal errors, or failure to fulfill their obligations to customers and society. This could affect customer trust and the bank's credibility, and in turn, reduce profits and increase the costs associated with addressing the issue. Reputational risk can also affect a bank's share price and market capitalization, and can have long-term implications on the bank's business and operations. Therefore, banks must ensure that they conduct business in an ethical and transparent manner, and monitor and manage reputation risks well to ensure their reputation remains good and stable.

Bibliometric studies are a branch of science that analyzes and evaluates scientific publications and related information. It involves the use of statistical and informatics methodologies to assess the production, citation, and dissemination of knowledge in scientific literature. Bibliometric studies can be used to measure the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions and scientific fields, as well as to understand interactions and relationships between scientific fields and publications. It can also help in the identification and evaluation of trends and issues in the scientific literature. Some applications of bibliometric studies include citation network analysis, cluster analysis, and visibility analysis. Results from bibliometric studies can be used by researchers, government, and industry to understand developments and contributions in scientific fields and to determine future research directions.

VOSviewer is bibliometric software used for visualization and analysis of scientific publication data. It allows users to visualize citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis data in the form of graphs and diagrams that are intuitive and easy to accept. VOSviewer can help researchers and analysts carry out citation network analysis, find relationships between scientific fields, and understand trends and issues in scientific literature. It also helps in determining future research directions and gaining insight into the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions, and scientific fields. VOSviewer has an easy-to-use user interface and can be used together with data coming from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. It allows users to visualize and analyze publication data effectively and efficiently.

literature review study is a process that includes identification, evaluation, and synthesis of results from previous research on a specific topic. It aims to provide an overview of trends, issues, and advances in related fields and assist in understanding how previous research influences future research developments and directions. Literature review studies are usually conducted as part of the research process to ensure that researchers understand the existing research environment

and produce non-duplicative results. It also helps in determining problems and gaps in the existing literature and helps in the formulation of hypotheses and understanding of specific research areas. Literature review studies can be carried out by accessing scientific publication databases, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Researchers can also carry out manual searches through scientific journals and related books. Literature review studies must be carried out with a systematic and objective methodology to ensure that the results are accurate and valid.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is reputation risk. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on reputation risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sinta and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Reputation Risk " within the entire year period (2002-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics based on literature review studies.

Results and Discussion

1. Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Reputation Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are 91 international and national journals based on the results of data collection from the Perish/Harzing application during the period 2002 to 2022. There are 34 international journals indexed by Scopus. And there are 57 international and national journals indexed by Sinta around reputation risk research.

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding Reputation Risk by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2002	2	2009	1	2014	7	2019	7
2004	2	2010	2	2015	9	2020	6
2005	3	2011	3	2016	7	2021	6
2006	2	2012	5	2017	4	2022	10
2008	1	2013	7	2018	7		

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

2. Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Reputation Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are several things that need to be considered when knowing bibliometric results with software VOSviewer, namely: first, the software interface, namely the VOSviewer interface displays diagrams and graphs that visualize publication data. Users can open and explore these charts and graphs by clicking on specific items or zooming in on specific parts of the diagram. Second, visual components, namely several visual components that may appear in VOSviewer bibliometric results including nodes (representations of publications), lines (representations of citation relationships), and colors (representations of categories or topics). Third, citation network analysis, namely citation network analysis helps in determining relationships between publications and understanding how publications are related to each other. Larger nodes in the diagram represent more widely noted publications and relationships between nodes can help in understanding how publications are related. Fourth, cluster analysis, namely cluster analysis helps in determining relationships between topics or fields of science and understanding how publications are related to certain topics or fields of science. The colors in the diagram represent categories or topics and help in understanding how publications relate to different topics or fields of science. Fifth, citation analysis, namely citation analysis helps in determining the most noted publications and understanding how publications are related to each other. Larger nodes in the diagram represent more widely recorded publications and help in understanding how publications relate to each other. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around Reputation Risk

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer related to the research development map regarding reputation risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking, there are 14 clusters and 78 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 14 topic items, namely: bank capital, bank operational risk, bank reputation, banking industry, Boston, ESG issue, loss, market reaction, measuring reputational, operational risk, reputational loss, reputational risk, risk culture, south African banking sector.
- Cluster 2, consists of 9 topic items, namely: BPRS, financial crisis, financial performance, financing, law, Indonesia, Islamic banking, reputation, risk.
- Cluster 3, consists of 8 topic items, namely: awareness, firm, insurance industry, large banking organization, management, reputation risk management, reputational capital, value.
- Cluster 4, consists of 8 topic items, namely: banking, conflicts, finance, interest, operational risk management, regulatory perspective, reputational implications, technological opportunity.
- Cluster 5, consists of 7 topic items, namely: bank regulation, country, developing countries, government, international standards, politics, political economy.
- Cluster 6, consists of 6 topic items, namely: bank risk, banking activity, business reputation, essence, risk, theoretical subtraction.
- Cluster 7, consists of 6 topic items, namely: commercial banks, continuous monitoring banks, Islamic banks, reputation risk, risk management, terms reputation.
- Cluster 8, consists of 5 topic items, namely: assessment, bank customer, bank reputational risk, internal fraud, reputational risk impact.
- Cluster 9, consists of 5 topic items, namely: banks, European investment banks, financial markets, modern information systems, reputational risk.
- Cluster 10, consists of 3 topic items, namely: bank liquidity, bank loans, reputation.
- Cluster 11, consists of 3 topic items, namely: banking system, reputational risk management, trust.
- Cluster 12, consists of 2 topic items, namely: bank reputation risk, court.
- Cluster 13, consists of 1 topic item, namely: banking sector.
- Cluster 14, consists of 1 topic item, namely: banking the current approach.

3. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Definition and Objectives of Reputation Risk Management

First, the definition of Reputation Risk. Reputation risk in banking is the potential for loss arising from damage or loss of the bank's image and reputation as a trusted financial institution. This can happen due to various things, such as ethical controversies, financial scandals, or misuse of customer data. Reputational risk can affect customer trust and bank credibility, and can result in reduced profits, increased marketing costs, and even loss of business. Therefore, banks must ensure that they understand and manage reputation risks well to ensure long-term business and reputation sustainability.

Second, the aim of Reputation Risk management is to ensure that the bank maintains and strengthens its positive image in the eyes of the public and financial markets. Reputation risk management in banking has several main objectives, including: (1) Reputation risk management ensures that banks do not experience reputational losses which result in business losses and financial losses; (2) Banks must maintain good integrity and reputation in order to maintain the trust of customers and other stakeholders; (3) Banks must ensure that their business activities do not harm the public and maintain a positive reputation; (4) Reputation risk management ensures that the bank has a positive reputation that influences

share prices and company value; and (5) Banks that have a good reputation will have greater competitive advantages compared to other banks. Thus, reputation risk management in banking aims to ensure that the bank has a good reputation and has a positive impact on the bank's business and financial performance.

4. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Reputation Risk Monitoring

Findings in this research topic include:

First, the authority and responsibilities of the Board of Commissioners include: (1) Supervising banking risk management strategies and policies, including reputation risk; (2) Ensure that the banking risk management system meets applicable standards and regulations; (3) Evaluate and monitor the implementation of policies and procedures to manage reputation risk; (4) Provide input and suggestions to the Board of Directors on how to overcome and manage reputation risks; (5) Ensure that reputation risk reporting and evaluation mechanisms are effective and adequate; (6) Carrying out inspections and investigations of reputation risk reports and appropriate follow-up; (7) Ensure that banks have adequate procedures and mechanisms to handle crisis situations and restore reputation; and (8) Communicate with external parties, including regulators and the public, to ensure that banking has a good image and solid reputation.

Second, the authority and responsibilities of the Board of Directors include: (1) The Board determines policies and procedures that help manage the bank's reputation risk and ensure that the bank complies with applicable regulations; (2) Monitor and evaluate the bank's reputation periodically to ensure that the bank continues to maintain a positive image and improves it if necessary; (3) Ensure that the bank has procedures and mechanisms to address threats to the bank's reputation, such as monitoring media reports and conducting internal investigations; and (4) Ensure that the bank has good openness and transparency practices and ensures that the information received by the public is accurate and accountable.

Third, related to Human Resources. Human resources (HR) play an important role in managing reputation risk in the banking sector. Banks must ensure that their staff have the necessary skills and knowledge to perform their duties well and meet applicable industry and regulatory standards. Competent and well-trained staff also help ensure that the service provided to customers meets expectations and maintains the bank's positive image. Therefore, banks must ensure that they employ and train staff who have integrity and good ethics, and ensure that they understand how their behavior can affect the bank's reputation. This can be done by ensuring that staff understand the banking code of conduct and through training and sensitization sessions on ethics and professionalism. In addition, banks must also ensure that recruitment, career development and performance management systems ensure that staff have the opportunity to develop and fulfill their potential, and motivate them to maintain high standards in carrying out their duties.

Fourth, related to Reputation Risk Management Organization. The Reputation Risk Management Organization (ORMR) is a unit formed by banks to monitor and manage reputation risks that may occur in bank business. ORMOR has an important role in ensuring that banks are able to maintain and strengthen their reputation, as well as minimizing the negative impact of various reputation risks that may arise. ORMOR works in coordination with various other units within banking, such as finance, legal, communications and information security departments, to ensure that banks have adequate procedures and systems to manage and monitor reputation risks. ORMOR also has the task of monitoring and identifying potential reputation risks that may occur, and evaluating and testing existing systems and procedures to ensure that the bank is ready to overcome reputation risks. ORMOR also has a role in

helping banks to strengthen their reputation by carrying out activities aimed at increasing public trust in banks. ORMR also has the task of communicating with various parties, including the media and the public, to ensure that the information conveyed to the public is accurate and timely.

5. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Strategy, Risk Level, Policies, Procedures and Limits in Reputation Risk Management

First, Reputation Risk management strategy. Reputation risk management is one of the important things for banking, because the bank's reputation greatly influences the trust and continuity of the bank's business itself. The following are several reputation risk management strategies in banking: (1) Banks must monitor and evaluate their actions and policies continuously to ensure that they do not pose a risk to their reputation; (2) Banks must have clear and consistently implemented policies and procedures to reduce risks to their reputation; (3) Banks must provide training and education to their employees on how to manage and minimize reputation risk; (4) Banks must be open and transparent in reporting their actions and policies to maintain public trust and reduce risks to their reputation; (5) Banks can work with external parties such as regulators, governments and consumers to ensure that they meet standards and best practices in reputation risk management; and (6) Banks must be prepared and available to respond promptly and appropriately to any allegations or issues that impact their reputation in order to address and remedy the situation as quickly as possible.

Second, the level of risk to be taken (Risk Appetite) and risk tolerance (Risk Tolerance) on Reputation Risk. Risk Appetite and Risk Tolerance are two different concepts in reputation risk management in banking. Risk Appetite is the amount of risk that a bank or company is prepared to take in achieving its goals. This involves determining risk tolerance limits and how certain risks will be accepted or rejected based on strategic decisions. Risk Appetite can usually be expressed in the form of a number or scale that determines the level of risk a company can accept. Risk Tolerance, on the other hand, is how far a company or individual is prepared to suffer losses or bear risks in achieving its goals. This involves understanding how risks will affect expected outcomes and how individuals or companies will react to different risk situations. In terms of reputational risk in banking, Risk Appetite and Risk Tolerance must be implemented carefully to ensure that banks can protect and maintain their positive image. Banks must have a high Risk Appetite to make investments and make business decisions that can help them achieve their goals, but must also have a low Risk Tolerance to ensure that they do not take excessive risks and endanger their reputation.

Third, Reputation Risk policy. A reputation risk policy in banking is a document that explains how a bank understands and manages the reputation risks it may face. Reputation is an important asset for a bank and can influence business performance and the bank's image in the eyes of the public. Therefore, it is critical for banks to have clear policies and procedures to manage reputation risk. Several things that are usually explained in reputation risk policies in banking include: (1) Definition of reputation risk, namely providing a clear understanding of what is meant by reputation risk and how this risk can affect the bank; (2) Risk identification, namely discussing how banks identify potential reputation risks, including through media monitoring, customer surveys and business performance evaluation; (3) Risk mitigation, namely providing guidance on how banks can overcome reputation risks through preventive actions and continuous monitoring; (4) Responsibilities of authorized parties, namely explaining the duties and responsibilities of authorized parties in managing reputation risk, including how they

work together to ensure effective policy implementation; and (5) Monitoring and evaluation system, which explains how the bank will monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of reputation risk policies and make necessary changes.

Fourth, Reputation Risk procedures. Reputational risk in banking is the potential loss arising from negative public views of a bank, both as a result of internal and external actions. In this case, reputation risk procedures in banking are as follows: (1) Risk identification, namely the first step in overcoming reputation risk is identifying potential sources of risk, such as unethical business practices, technical problems, financial scandals and environmental problems; (2) Risk evaluation, namely after identifying risks, banks must evaluate the level of risk and potential impact on business and reputation; (3) Developing a risk management strategy, namely the bank must develop a strategy to manage reputation risk, including ensuring that there are appropriate procedures and systems to monitor and resolve problems; (4) Monitoring and control, namely banks must monitor and control reputation risk through appropriate procedures and systems, and take corrective action if necessary; (5) Reporting and evaluation, namely banks must report and evaluate the results of reputation risk management periodically, and make improvements if necessary; and (6) Staff training and sensibilization, namely the bank must ensure that staff understand the importance of reputation and the procedures for managing it through training and sensibilization.

Fifth, Reputation Risk limit. Reputational risk limits in banking aim to limit the negative impact that might occur on a bank's reputation if a detrimental incident or event occurs. Reputational risks in banking can arise from various sources, such as operational errors, fraudulent acts, unprofessional actions, and so on. To limit reputation risk in banking, several actions that can be taken include: (1) Implementation of an Internal Control System, namely banks must ensure that their internal control system meets established standards and ensures that every action and transaction within the bank is carried out in an appropriate manner. correct and responsible; (2) Building good relationships with customers, namely banks must ensure that their customers are satisfied and have a good relationship with the bank, which can be done by providing good service and ensuring that every customer complaint is handled professionally and efficiently; (3) Carry out continuous monitoring and evaluation, namely banks must carry out continuous monitoring and evaluation of their policies and procedures to ensure that they are always up-to-date and meet established standards; (4) Ensuring transparency and accountability, namely the bank must ensure that every transaction and action carried out within the bank is transparent and accountable, and that the information provided to customers and the public is honest and accurate; and (5) Carrying out training and outreach, namely banks must ensure that each of their employees understands the importance of reputation and that they know how their actions and behavior can affect the bank's reputation. Training and socialization also aims to ensure that employees understand the standards set and act in accordance with these standards.

6. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Reputation Risk Identification, Measurement, Monitoring, Control and Information Systems

First, identify Reputation Risk. Identification of reputation risk in banking is very important because reputation is an important asset for a bank. The following are several steps to identify reputation risks in banking: (1) Internal Analysis, which involves evaluating bank strategies, procedures and practices to determine whether there is the potential to affect the bank's reputation; (2) Media Monitoring, namely monitoring media and information sources to monitor developments in news and information that may affect the bank's reputation; (3) Customer survey, namely conducting a customer survey to understand how customers view the bank and

whether there are any problems that affect the bank's reputation; (4) External analysis, namely this analysis involves evaluating the business and economic environment to determine whether there are external factors that influence the bank's reputation; (5) Concurrent monitoring, namely monitoring concurrency activities and practices to ensure that the bank remains competitive and maintains a good reputation; and (6) Trend analysis, namely conducting trend analysis to determine market trends and whether there are trends that affect the bank's reputation.

Second, measuring Reputation Risk can be carried out using various approaches, some of which are: (1) Survey approach, which is the approach most often used, namely by conducting surveys of customers, employees, business partners or the general public to find out their views on reputation. bank. This survey can be conducted by telephone, internet, or via print media; (2) Data approach, namely a data-based approach, namely by collecting and analyzing data about the bank's reputation, such as financial reports, media monitoring and survey results; (3) Mathematical model approach, namely an approach based on mathematical modeling, namely using an algorithm to measure reputation risk based on available data; and (4) Collaborative approach, namely an approach based on cooperation, namely by collaborating with other companies or industry associations to obtain information about the bank's reputation. Then, after obtaining information about the bank's reputation, this data can be processed and analyzed to determine the level of reputation risk. Some banks also implement regular monitoring systems to ensure that reputation risks remain within reasonable limits.

Third, monitoring Reputation Risk, is an important part of bank risk management. The goal is to ensure that the bank has a good reputation and maintains it over time. The following are several ways that banks can monitor reputation risk: (1) Social media analysis, namely monitoring activities and conversations on social media can help banks to understand public perceptions and track positive or negative trends related to the bank's reputation; (2) Customer surveys, namely banks can conduct surveys with customers to understand their perceptions of the bank and how they assess the bank's service and reputation; (3) Press monitoring, namely banks can monitor media publications to ensure that they have the latest information about what is written about the bank; (4) Reputation risk analysis, namely banks can analyze reputation risk by considering factors such as company policies, business practices and external conditions; and (5) Development of a response system, namely the bank must have an effective system to respond to and resolve situations that may affect the bank's reputation, such as regulatory issues or accusations of violating business ethics.

Fourth, controlling Reputation Risk. Controlling reputation risk in banking is very important because banks have a reputation that is very dependent on the trust and credibility received by customers and the public in general. The following are several steps that banks can take to control reputation risk: (1) Implementation of policies and procedures, namely banks must have clear and effective policies and procedures to overcome problems that have the potential to affect their reputation; (2) Product and service management, namely banks must ensure that their products and services meet ethical and legal standards, and ensure that the information provided to customers is clear and not confusing; (3) Monitoring and reporting, namely banks must monitor situations that have the potential to affect their reputation, and report problems that occur in a timely and effective manner; (4) Training and socialization, namely banks must ensure that their employees understand the importance of reputation risk and have the necessary skills to overcome it; (5) Collaboration with external parties, namely the bank must build good

relationships with external parties, such as regulators, the media and the public, to help overcome problems that have the potential to affect its reputation; and (6) Evaluation and improvement, namely banks must regularly evaluate the policies and procedures implemented to overcome reputation risks, and improve them if necessary.

Fifth, the Reputation Risk Management Information System (SIMRR), is an information technology system used by banks to monitor, analyze and manage reputation risks faced by companies. It involves collecting, analyzing and interpreting information about banking reputation from various sources such as the media, customers, suppliers and regulations. By using SIMRR, banks can identify potential reputation risks such as actions that are detrimental to customers, environmental issues, actions that violate regulations, and other problems. This information can be used to make decisions and prioritize actions to minimize risks and maintain banking reputation. In addition, SIMRR can also help banks to track and report actions taken to address reputation risks and monitor the effectiveness of these actions. This enables banks to continuously optimize reputation risk management processes and ensure that they meet appropriate regulatory and governance standards.

Sixth, Reputation Risk Internal Control System, namely a set of procedures and mechanisms implemented by banks to monitor and manage risks related to their reputation. This includes identifying, evaluating and controlling risks that may affect the bank's reputation, both positively and negatively. The aim is to ensure that banks are protected from potential reputational losses and to maintain and build a positive image of them. Several ways that can be used to manage reputation risk in banking include: (1) Media Monitoring, namely banks must monitor the media regularly to find out what is happening and how the public views their bank; (2) Social listening, i.e. banks must monitor social networks and discussion websites to understand what people are talking about and how they view their bank; (3) Risk analysis, namely banks must carry out risk analysis to understand and prioritize the reputation risks they face; (4) Training and education, namely banks must ensure that their employees understand the importance of reputation and how reputation risk can affect the bank; and (5) Procedures and control mechanisms, namely banks must have adequate procedures and mechanisms to manage reputation risks and ensure that they always maintain a positive image.

7. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Problems in Reputation Risk

There are several findings in this research topic, including:

First, the influence of reputation risk on underpricing. Underpricing is a phenomenon where the share price at the time of the IPO (Initial Public Offering) is lower than the market price after the share is listed on the stock exchange. This underpricing can be caused by several things, such as lack of information, the influence of public opinion, and company reputation. The influence of reputation risk management on underpricing in banking is very significant. Banks that have a good and stable reputation will have a lower level of underpricing compared to banks that have a bad or unstable reputation. This is because investors will have more trust and confidence in banks that have a good reputation, so they will be more interested in investing in these shares, causing the underpricing level to be lower.

Second, the influence of reputation risk management on Murabahah margins. The influence of reputation risk management on Murabahah margins can be seen from two sides, namely:

- (1) Good reputation risk management will help strengthen the bank's reputation, which in turn will strengthen the bank's image as a trustworthy and reliable bank. This will help banks to increase Murabahah margins, as customers will

trust the bank more and be more inclined to carry out transactions with the bank.

- (2) Poor reputation risk management can negatively affect Murabahah margins. If a bank is hit by a scandal or actions that are detrimental to customers, this will affect the bank's reputation and its image as a trustworthy bank. This will reduce customer trust in the bank and reduce the number of transactions carried out by customers, thereby affecting Murabahah margins.

Third, reputation risk management within the National Amil Zakat Institution (Laznas). This is very important because Laznas is responsible for protecting and maintaining their reputation as an institution responsible for managing zakat funds. The following are several ways to manage reputation risk at Laznas: (1) Transparency and accountability, namely Laznas must ensure that all activities and expenditures of zakat funds are recorded and announced transparently, so that the public can monitor and ensure that zakat funds are used according to the desired purpose; (2) Internal supervision, namely Laznas must ensure that there are effective internal control procedures and systems to monitor activities and ensure that all standards and regulations are met; (3) Risk mitigation, namely Laznas must ensure that they have a good plan to overcome and reduce risks that may arise, including reputation risks; (4) Effective communication, namely Laznas must ensure that they have an effective communication strategy to maintain and build their reputation, including through social media, annual reports, and direct communication with the public; (5) Collaborate with related parties, namely Laznas must collaborate with related parties such as the government, community organizations and other institutions to ensure that they have the same views and work together in efforts to build their reputation. By following these methods, Laznas can ensure that they have effective reputation risk management and ensure that they can maintain their reputation as a responsible and trustworthy amil zakat institution.

Fourth, mitigate reputation risk by using Action Control. Action control is one method that can be used to minimize reputation risk. It emphasizes proactive measures to control situations before they become major problems. Some ways to use action control to reduce reputation risk include: (1) Monitoring, namely monitoring the situation and tracking developments to determine what actions should be taken; (2) Training, namely ensuring that all staff understand and practice best practices in terms of business behavior and behavior; (3) Policies and procedures, namely establishing clear policies and procedures and ensuring that all staff understand and comply with them; (4) Environmental control, namely ensuring that the business environment meets the standards necessary to maintain a good reputation; (5) Communication, namely ensuring that all relevant parties understand reputation risks and the actions that must be taken to overcome them; (6) Investigation, namely carrying out timely and complete investigations into problems that have the potential to damage reputation; and (7) Rapid response, namely ensuring that appropriate action is taken as quickly as possible to limit negative impacts on reputation. These are just a few examples of how to use action controls to minimize reputation risk. It is important to ensure that the actions taken are truly appropriate to the particular situation and context, and always consider the potential impact on the company's reputation.

Fifth, mitigate reputation risk by using Result Control. One way to mitigate reputation risk is to use Result Control. Results Control is a process of controlling and monitoring business activities and results to ensure that they comply with established standards and objectives. This helps a company to identify and minimize risks that may affect its reputation, such as inappropriate policies and procedures, errors in reporting, or unethical business practices. By conducting Results Control

effectively, companies can ensure that they meet generally accepted standards of ethics and professionalism, and maintain a good reputation. It also helps companies to respond quickly and appropriately if problems occur, thereby minimizing potential reputational damage.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding reputation risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking during the period 2002 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 91 research articles.
- In the mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, research developments regarding reputation risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking are divided into 14 clusters and 78 items. Cluster 1 consists of 14 items, cluster 2 consists of 9 items, cluster 3 consists of 8 items, cluster 4 consists of 8 items, cluster 5 consists of 7 items, cluster 6 consists of 6 items, cluster 7 consists of 6 items, cluster 8 consists of 5 items, cluster 9 consists of 5 items, cluster 10 consists of 3 items, cluster 11 consists of 3 items, cluster 12 consists of 2 items, cluster 13 consists of 1 item, and cluster 14 consists of 1 item.
- Based on a literature review, there are 5 main research themes surrounding reputation risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: (1) Definition and objectives of risk management; (2) Risk monitoring; (3) Strategy, risk level, policies, procedures, limits; (4) Identification, measurement, monitoring, control, information systems; and (5) Risk issues.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the literature review study can be explained in a more complex way.

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